

Application Of Artificial Intelligence in Teaching and Learning in Secondary Schools in Anambra State

By

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Abstract

This study determined the application of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State. Three research questions guided the study and three null hypotheses were tested. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design using a population of 571 public secondary school teachers in the area of the study. The entire population was studied without sampling because the size was manageable. A structured questionnaire developed by the researchers was used for data collection. Cronbach Alpha method was used to establish the reliability which yielded coefficient values of 0.81, 0.79 and 0.83 for the three clusters. Out of the 690 copies of the instruments administered, only 571 copies were retrieved. This number (571) represented 90% of the questionnaires administered. Mean, standard deviation and ANOVA were used to analyze the data. The results showed that AI-teachers agreed on the artificial intelligence tools available in secondary schools, benefits and challenges of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State. The results showed that experience do not significantly influenced the mean ratings of the respondents on the artificial intelligence tools available for teaching and learning, benefits and challenges of applying these tools in teaching and learning. Therefore, it was recommended among others that there is a need for comprehensive professional development programmes aimed at equipping teachers with the necessary skills and competencies to effectively apply AI tools in teaching and learning. These programmes should focus on providing training in AI literacy, data analytics, and instructional design to enable educators to create AI-enhanced learning experiences that align with curriculum objectives.

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Introduction

Globally, education is considered very important for personal and societal development. Nigeria regards education as an instrument for the promotion of national development as well as affecting desirable social change (Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014). According to Obidile and Obi (2020), education is an essential element of human development and existence. Universally, education is an instrument for social, political, scientific and technological development. It empowers young people with knowledge and skills, which in turn provide them with access to productive employment and meaningful contribution to national development. As affirmed by Ubulom and Ogwunte (2017), education is the most powerful agent for social transformation, national stability, security, unity, and prosperity. This is why the Nigerian sees education as an instrument per excellence for individual and national development.

Thus, the education system in Nigeria has been delineated into different levels; mainly pre-secondary, secondary and tertiary levels. Secondary school education is the form of education students receive after primary school and before the tertiary stage. Udalla in Nnaji for and Ejikeme (2020) noted that the importance of secondary education lies in its position both as the bridge between secondary and tertiary education and the agent for preparing individuals for useful living in the society. As indicated by the Federal Republic Nigeria (2014) in the National Policy on Education, the broad goals of secondary education are preparing people for useful living in the society and for higher education. This has made it imperative that it should, among others, supply trained manpower in the applied science, technology and commerce at sub-professional levels; inspire its students with the desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence; raise a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others; and respect the dignity of labour.

Following the objectives of secondary schools, teaching and learning accelerates the positive molding of students' attitudes and character into responsible Nigerian citizens. However, these objectives can only be achieved if the instructional strategies are modified to suit the technological demands of modern offices, schools and the business environment. The teaching and learning in Nigerian secondary schools is basically of great importance to the contemporary Nigerian society. Numerous innovative approaches have been introduced to aid efficient and effective teaching and learning. Traditional teaching and learning have changed (Yufei, Saleh, Jiahui, & Abdullah, 2020), and students and teachers dug new ideas for teaching reform. The world is rapidly trending technologically and this has permeated every field of human endeavour including education. As a result of this revolution, information, ideas,

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lifestyles and innovations easily spread to every part of the world. The nature of instructional preparations and delivery in education has also been revolutionized and secondary education programmes are affected by these rapid changes in technology and automation. The effectiveness of teachers and instruction are the most important factors in influencing student learning. The role of technology in the field of education is numerous. It is included as part of curriculum, as an instructional delivery system and a tool to enhance the entire learning process (Raja & Nagasubramani, 2018). One of the new educational technologies in education is artificial intelligence.

Artificial intelligence is defined as technologies used to allow computers to perform tasks that would otherwise require human intelligence, such as virtual perception, speech recognition and language translation (Fanning, 2024). Artificial intelligence is a technology where machines can learn and understand logic like humans. This technology is said to be able to help simplify human life which is very complex (Fitria, 2021). AI itself works by combining the presence of several data, iterative processing, and intelligent algorithms. This allows the software to learn automatically from patterns or features in the data. Artificial intelligence education software development has revolutionized traditional learning methods, from mobile digital courses to online references and virtual classrooms. With the development of technology artificial intelligence has impacted globally on education. AI plays a pivotal role in encouraging teaching and learning; it gives teachers new way of teaching to deliver information to students and provided students with new and proper ways of learning.

Artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative technology with the potential to revolutionize various industries, including education. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in understanding the impact of AI on students' learning experiences (Robert, Potter & Frank, 2024). AI technologies, such as machine learning, natural language processing, and data analytics, are being leveraged to develop innovative educational tools and platforms that can enhance the way students learn, engage, and succeed in their educational pursuits. These technologies create a virtual space that can be fully controlled, so that the learning outcomes can be optimized. AI technologies facilitate collaborative learning environments. Intelligent tutoring systems and virtual learning assistants can support group discussions, provide guidance, and encourage collaboration among students. These AI-powered tools can simulate real-world scenarios, promote active participation, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills. By applying AI in education technologies, educators can determine student needs more precisely, keep students more engaged, improve learning, and adapt teaching accordingly to boost learning outcomes (Issayeva, 2023).

The application of artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching and learning in secondary school brings forth numerous benefits that positively impact students' learning experiences. The role of artificial intelligence in education reshapes teaching and learning in innovative ways. AI serves as a facilitator of creativity by generating interactive learning materials, such as simulations and virtual labs, enhancing content beyond traditional methods. Using AI tools can guide educators

to use a more interactive teaching approach which may result in increased engagement and motivation in the class as well as improved learning objectives. One major opportunity for in Artificial Intelligence in education is the role that Artificial Intelligence can play in solving workload related problems experienced by teachers. By integrating AI into classrooms, teachers can personalize learning experiences, streamline administrative tasks and provide more effective support to students. In recent years, teachers have often shown dissatisfaction with the high workload experienced in education (Alabi, 2022). This increased workload is partly due to the additional administrative tasks that teachers have been given with the existing range of tasks as well as due to the reduction of new teachers entering the workforce. AI makes learning more interactive and engaging through gamified content and adaptive learning platforms. These games use AI to provide tasks and challenges that adapt to student responses, promoting active participation and understanding of complex subjects. AI in education helps educators identify gaps in student knowledge and provide targeted feedback to improve learning outcomes.

The challenges for the teachers in secondary schools is no longer centred on covering the course content or adopting appropriate teaching or pedagogical aids but embracing artificial intelligence in teaching and learning (Adlawan, 2024). Introduction of artificial intelligence in secondary schools is very complex and enormous. One of the biggest challenges is that everyone learns differently. It is difficult for teachers to accurately grasp each student's real learning situation, leading to the teaching design and teaching process, difficult to focus on each student's real learning needs, resulting in a waste of energy, time and teaching resources. Another challenge is that AI can be costly to implement for teachers and not all schools and educational institutions have a dedicated budget for investing in AI tools and technologies. There is therefore the need for teachers to be proactive in their approach to this technology as well as the utilization of these facilities in teaching and learning situations to improve student outcomes and promote equity in the classroom.

Teachers to be used in this study come from secondary schools with different levels of educational attainment and years of experience which may influence their level of skills in applying artificial intelligence for instructional purposes. This provides one with respondent variable years of experience (0-5 years/6-10 years/above 10 years) which will enrich the study. Experience is the number of years or the period a worker has been performing assigned duties. The term experience is defined as professional growth that takes place in the educator as a result of continued stay, or study on the job and other related processes. The general notion according to Obasi (2016) is that employees with high level of experience perform better than those with lower experience. This conception is still a matter of great debate among researchers in education and management sciences. Teachers with more years of experience in new technologies tends to implement more innovative methodologies through emerging technologies than teachers with less years of experience (Oleksiuk and Olesiuk, 2020). Artificial intelligence can be deployed to solve various problems hindering the effective implementation of teaching programmes in secondary schools across the country. Based on this, the study examines the

application of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning of government in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

The broad aims of secondary education according to Nigeria National Policy on Education, FRN (2014), are preparation of students for useful living within the society and for higher education. The future of a country is on the quality of education given to its citizens, because, education assures the future of the society and provides continuity. If these objectives will be achieved then efforts should be made to provide innovative pedagogies and encourage their adequate utilization. Despite the imperativeness and significance of the secondary education especially in this democratic dispensation, the teaching and learning in Nigeria's secondary school system has been frosted with challenges resulting in poor performance of students in external examinations, and failure on their parts to imbibe the culture of social and political assets for national development. These challenges are traceable to poor motivation and a lack of innovative strategies such as artificial intelligence. With advancement in technology in the 21st century, artificial intelligence has become an invaluable technology for teaching, learning and research in education. AI has so many advantages on teaching and learning. However, despite these numerous advantages, some teachers still find it challenging in transiting from the analogue to the digital in teaching and learning. Teachers may have a limited understanding of how the technology works and may lack the technical expertise to fully comprehend the algorithms used in AI tools and how they affect assessment outcomes. Without adequate training, teachers may be unable to use the tools effectively, leading to inaccurate assessments. AI-powered tools require a stable and reliable technology infrastructure. Technical difficulties, such as power outages, internet disruptions, or software malfunctions, can disrupt the assessment process, leading to inaccurate or incomplete assessments. This appears to have been seriously affecting the students' academic performance as regards to the acquisition of appropriate skills. As a result, the morale and interest of students is low. Hence, there is need for application of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine the application of artificial intelligence in the teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. Artificial intelligence tools available in the teaching and learning in secondary schools.
2. Benefits of applying artificial intelligence in the teaching and learning in secondary schools.
3. Challenges of application of artificial intelligence in the teaching and learning in secondary schools.

Research Question

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The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the artificial intelligence tools available in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What are the benefits of applying artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. What are the challenges of application of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the respondents mean ratings on the artificial intelligence tools available in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State based of years of experience.
2. There is no significant difference in the respondents mean ratings on the benefits of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State based of years of experience.
3. There is no significant difference in the respondents mean ratings on the challenges of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State based of years of experience.

Method

Descriptive survey research design was adopted in this study. According to Nworgu (2015), descriptive survey research design is one which aims at collecting data and describing in a systematic manner the characteristics, features or facts about a given population using a questionnaire. The study was carried out in state-owned public secondary schools in Anambra State. Anambra is a State in South Eastern Nigeria. The target population of the study consisted of all the 6, 899 teachers in all the 266 public secondary schools in the area of the study. Sample for the study were 690 teachers (10% of the population) in 26 selected public secondary schools in Anambra State. The proportionate stratified- random sampling technique was adopted. The instrument for data collection was researcher's structured questionnaire. Data for the study were collected using a structured questionnaire titled "Application of Artificial Intelligence in Teaching and Learning Questionnaire (AAITLQ)". The respondents were requested to rate the items on a 4-point rating scale of strongly agreed (SA), agreed (A), disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD) with values 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instrument was validated by three experts in the field. Cronbach Alpha method was used to establish the reliability of the instrument. The reliability test yielded coefficient values of 0.81, 0.78 and 0.83 for the three clusters. The researcher administered 690 copies of the questionnaire to the respondents with the help of five research assistants who were briefed on the method of data collection and retrieval. The respondents were given sufficient time to complete and return the copies of the instrument.

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The exercise lasted two weeks. Out of the 690 copies of the instruments administered, only 571 copies were retrieved. This number (571) represented 90% of the questionnaires administered. Data collected were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and ANOVA. The application of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 was used for data analysis. For the hypotheses, p-value was used for decision making. Where the calculated p-value was less than the stipulated level of significance 0.05 (i.e. $p < 0.05$), it implies that there was a significant difference between respondents' mean scores and the null hypothesis was rejected. On the other hand, if the p-value was greater than or equal to the alpha level of 0.05 ($p \geq 0.05$), it meant that there was no significant difference in the respondents mean scores and was not rejected.

Results

Research Question 1

What are the artificial intelligence tools available in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1

Mean ratings on the artificial intelligence tools available in teaching and learning
N= 571

S/NO AI tools available	Mean	SD	Decision
1. Virtual reality systems	3.22	0.46	Agreed
2. Chat bots	3.17	0.45	Agreed
3. Intelligent tutoring systems	3.37	0.48	Agreed
4. Smart content	3.46	0.50	Agreed
5. Adaptive learning platforms	3.20	0.46	Agreed
6. Essay grading software	3.47	0.51	Agreed
7. Virtual mentor	3.48	0.49	Agreed
8. Intelligent simulation game	3.33	0.47	Agreed
Cluster Mean	3.34		Agreed

The analysis in Table 1 shows that the cluster mean of 3.34 which indicated that teachers agreed on the artificial intelligence tools available in the teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State. The item by item analysis shows that all the items with the mean scores ranging from 3.17 to 3.48 agreed on the artificial intelligence tools available for teaching and learning. There is homogeneity in responses indicating a greater consensus of opinion.

Research Question 2

What are the benefits of applying artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State?

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Table 2

Mean ratings on the benefits of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning

N = 571

S/NO	Benefits of artificial intelligence	Mean	SD	Decision
1.	AI enables the provision of timely and constructive feedback to students.	3.33	.53	Agreed
2.	Facilitates collaborative learning environments	3.31	.53	Agreed
3.	Improved student engagement	3.21	.60	Agreed
4.	Increased confidence in students	3.23	.62	Agreed
5.	Transformation of classroom into an interactive learning environment	3.10	.57	Agreed
6.	Adaptive assessment and feedback	3.00	.68	Agreed
7.	Enhancing accessibility to quality educational resources	3.11	.67	Agreed
8.	Reduction in human error	3.27	.69	Agreed
Cluster Mean		3.20		Agreed

Table 2 shows that the cluster mean of 3.20 indicated that teachers agreed on the benefits of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State. The item by item analysis shows that teachers agreed that all the items were the benefits of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning. The standard deviation showed that there is homogeneity amongst responses indicating a greater consensus of opinion.

Research Question 3

What are the challenges of application of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 3

Mean ratings on the challenges of application of AI in teaching and learning in secondary schools
N = 571

S/NO Challenges of AI	Mean	SD	
1. Decreases the thinking power of the students	3.29	.46	Agreed
2. Overuse of AI for assignments may lead to passive participation in class discussions	3.23	.42	Agreed
3. Uneven distribution of AI education resources	3.17	.38	Agreed
4. Potential decrease in academic retention rates due to reduced human interaction	3.34	.48	Agreed
5. Inadequate fund for acquisition and training	3.39	.49	Agreed
6. Costly to implement for teachers	3.27	.45	Agreed
7. Dependence on technology	3.32	.46	Agreed
8. Lack of basics technology skills	3.21	.41	Agreed
Cluster Mean	3.28		Agreed

Table 3 shows that the cluster mean of 3.28 indicated that teachers agreed on the challenges of application of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State. The item by item analysis shows that teachers agreed that all the items were the challenges of application of artificial intelligence in secondary school. The standard deviation showed that there is homogeneity amongst responses indicating a greater consensus of opinion.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the respondents mean ratings on the artificial intelligence tools available in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State based of years of experience.

Table 4

Summary of ANOVA on the artificial intelligence tools available in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State

Source of Variance	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	P-value	Decision
Between Groups	5.871	2	2.935			
				.258	.773	Not Sig
Within Groups	1138.886	568	11.389			
Total	1144.757	570				

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Table 4 shows that at 568 degree of freedom, years of experience did not significantly influence the mean ratings of teachers on the artificial intelligence tools available in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State. F-ratio is .258 and P-value (.773) which is greater than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance (P-value > alpha level). Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the respondents mean ratings on the benefits of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State based of years of experience.

Table 5
Summary of ANOVA on the benefits of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State

Source of Variance	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	P-value	Decision
Between Groups	.861	2	.430			
				.038	.963	Not Sig
Within Groups	1143.897	568	11.439			
Total	1144.757	570				

Table 5 shows that at 568 degree of freedom, experience do not significantly influenced the mean ratings of the respondents on the benefits of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State. F-ratio is .038 and P-value (.963) which is greater than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance (P-value > alpha level). Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the respondents mean ratings on the challenges of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State based of years of experience.

Table 6
Summary of ANOVA on the challenges of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State

Source of Variance	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	P-value	Decision
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Between Groups	12.840	2	6.420			
				1.735	.182	Not Sig
Within Groups	369.918	568	3.699			
Total	382.757	570				

Table 6 shows that at 568 degree of freedom, experience do not significantly influenced the mean ratings of the respondents on the challenges of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State. F-ratio is 1.735 and P-value (.182) which is greater than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance (P-value > alpha level). Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected.

Discussion

Results of the study indicated that teachers agreed on the artificial intelligence tools available in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State. The findings of the study agree with that of Singh and Jain (2022) who stated that artificial intelligence application in educational institutions empowers teachers to use AI as a tool to enhance instruction and to create totally new educational environment which both encourage and require new behaviour in the teachers and students. These tools can provide educators with valuable insights into student performance, learning outcomes, and instructional effectiveness. In support of this, Huang et al. (2023) asserted that AI-powered tools can help automate many aspects of the assessment process, saving time and reducing the burden on educators.

Results of the study indicated that teachers agreed on the benefits of application of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in consonance with the findings of Takyar (2022) who stated that the impact of AI in education is its ability to provide individualized learning paths for students based on their unique needs, learning styles, and abilities. This helps to ensure that students receive the support and resources they need to succeed, regardless of their background or skill level. AI in education helps educators identify gaps in student knowledge and provide targeted feedback to improve learning outcomes.

Results of the study revealed that teachers agreed on the challenges of application of artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in secondary schools in Anambra State. The findings are similar with the findings of Singh (2024) who observed that there are a lot challenges associated with artificial intelligence in teaching and learning in educational institutions. Singh observed that AI takes out the thinking power from students and makes them more dependent on technology for everything instead of learning how to do things themselves, maintenance problems, communication barriers, data problems, financial problems, laziness in the students among others.

Conclusion

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Artificial intelligence are fast growing in Nigerian educational institutions because of their relevance in equipping the students with skills, knowledge, attitude needed in the world of work as they graduate into producers of goods and services. The challenges of using these artificial intelligence tools for pedagogical delivery have undoubtedly affected teaching, learning and research, and its integration has helped revitalize teachers and students alike. It is important that these technologies must be adequately provided in secondary schools to enable the students acquire technology skills which will be needed for self employment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. There is a need for comprehensive professional development programmes aimed at equipping teachers with the necessary skills and competencies to effectively apply AI tools in teaching and learning.
2. The educational institutions should prioritize investment in AI infrastructure and resources to create a conducive environment for innovation and experimentation.
3. Government should increase funding of secondary education for the development of artificial intelligence in all public secondary schools across the country.
4. Institutions should establish mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating the impact of AI initiatives on teaching effectiveness, student engagement, and learning outcomes to inform future decision-making and investment priorities

REFERENCES

- Adlawan, D. (2024). The pros and cons of AI in education and how it will impact teachers in 2024. *ClassPoint Education Trends Classroom tips*.
- Alabi E. B. (2021). *Availability and utilization of instructional resources for the teaching of business education*. Lambert Academic Publishing.

- Nnajofofor, F. N. & Ejikeme, C.E. (2020). Teachers' utilization of instructional technology for quality teaching of Business Education in secondary schools in Enugu state, Nigeria. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 6(12) 207-226.
- Fanning, J. (2024). AI based assessment in education (AIBA): evidence review. *james.fanning@educationscotland.gov.scot*
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014). *National policy on education*. Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Fitria, T. N. (2021). *Artificial intelligence in education: Using AI tools for teaching and learning process*. Proceeding Seminar Nasional, Senin, 20, 134-147
- Huang, A. Y., Lu, O. H., & Yang, S. J. (2023a). Effects of artificial intelligence-enabled personalized recommendations on learners' learning engagement, motivation, and outcomes in a flipped classroom. *Computers & Education*, 194, 104684. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2022.104684>
- Issayeva, L. (2023). AI in education. ATP Conference in Dallas, TX.
- Nworgu, B. G. (2015). *Educational research: Basic issues and methodology*. Wisdom publishers.
- Obasi, N. F. (2016). *A study on factors influencing the administrative effectiveness of secondary school principals in Port Harcourt Metropolis*. Unpublished M.Ed Thesis, Department of Educational Management, University of Port Harcourt.
- Obidile, J. I. & Obi, O. C. (2020). Assessment of Adequacy, Availability and Extent of Utilization of Instructional Materials in the Teaching of Business Studies in

- Secondary Schools in Anambra State. *African Journal Research Review*, 14(57), 52-60. <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/afrrrev/article/view/195266>
- Oleksiuk, V. and Oleksiuk, O. (2020). Methodology of teaching cloud technologies to future computer science teachers. *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, 2643:592–608.
- Raja, R., & Nagasubramani, P. C. (2018), Impact of modern technology in education. *Journal of Applied and Advanced Research*, 3(1), 533-535.
- Robert, A., Potter, K., & Frank, L. (2024). The impact of artificial intelligence on students' learning experience.
- Singh, R. J. (2023). Transforming higher education: The power of artificial intelligence. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research in Arts, Science and Technology*, 1(3), 13-18.
- Singh, S., & Jain, P. (2022). Applications of artificial intelligence for the development of sustainable agriculture. In: Kumar, P., Tomar, R. S., Bhat, J. A., Dobriyal, M., Rani, M. (eds) *Agro-biodiversity and Agri-ecosystem Management*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-0928-3_16
- Takyar, A. (2022). AI in education: Use cases, benefits, solution and implementation. LeewayHertz's Developers. The Learning Lab
- Yufeia, L., Salehb, S., Jiahuic, H., & Syed, S. M. (2020). Review of the application of artificial intelligence in education. *Integration (Amsterdam)*, 12(8), 1-15.